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Unraveling the Protolith Origin of Serpentinite Rocks from the Tengnoupal Area, Manipur Ophiolite Complex, Indo-Myanmar Range

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Abstract

Objective: This article mainly focuses on investigating the protolith origin of serpentinite rocks in and around Tengnoupal, within the Manipur Ophiolite Complex (MOC), using a combined petrographic and geochemical approach.

Methods: During fieldwork, samples were collected and cut into thin sections to reveal their mineralogical and textural relationships. Major oxides and trace elements were determined by XRF, and rare earth elements analysis was carried out by ICP-MS to determine the nature and origin of the rocks. **Findings:** The studied rock samples exhibit varying degrees of serpentinitization, ranging from partial to complete, and exhibit a pseudomorphic texture including mesh and hour structures replacing the original olivine and bastite texture replacing pyroxene. Geochemically, the analyzed rock types exhibit komatiitic affinity and are characterized by high magnesium numbers (Mg# average 84.4). The studied serpentinite rocks have lower Al/Si ratios (Average=0.05) and higher Mg/Si ratios (average= 0.95) in bulk rock compositions indicating a refractory abyssal mantle peridotite protolith when compared to the primitive mantle. The high Ti (range 300-480 ppm) and Cr (628-3186 ppm) contents indicate a subduction environment. In addition, the rock samples exhibit slight depletion chondrite-normalized Rare Earth Elements (REE) patterns ($(La/Yb)_N$ = average 0.87). The rocks exhibit spoon-shaped normalized Rare Earth Element patterns and primitive mantle are similar to mid-oceanic ridge abyssal mantle rocks.

Novelty: The origins of the rocks studied suggest a transitional phase between abyssal and subduction zone-related serpentinites, forming after harzburgite-peridotite. As subduction began, dehydrated orogenic peridotite from the abyssal serpentinites was thrust or obducted, forming the MOC serpentinites. This indicates that the serpentinite rocks in MOC share similarities with those found in mid-oceanic ridge environments, which is characteristic of a supra-subduction zone setting.

Keywords: Ultramafic rocks; Serpentinization; Suprasubduction zone; Abyssal; REE

1 Introduction

Ophiolite-related ultramafic rocks are found along the Indo-Myanmar range within the Manipur Ophiolite Complex. These ultramafic rocks formed in the Earth's upper mantle and subsequently transformed into serpentinites, either completely or partially, through the interaction with crustal fluids during their movement to their current tectonic location. Ophiolites provide valuable insights into the evolution of ancient oceanic crust and mantle beneath spreading centers, including Mid-Ocean Ridge (MOR) and Supra-Subduction Zone (SSZ) tectonic settings^(1,2). They form in diverse tectonic environments, both related and unrelated to subduction processes⁽³⁾. From the study of the geochemical composition of ophiolitic rocks various tectonic environments such as sea-floor spreading zones, hotspots, backarc and forearc basins (SSZ environments), and other extensional magmatic tectonic settings, including those associated with plumes can be identified and understand the nature of mantle sources. In addition, ophiolites also provide information about the metamorphic, magmatic, and tectonic processes of the oceanic crust and upper mantle⁽⁴⁾. Ophiolitic mantle rocks are primarily important for understanding the palaeotectonic development of the oceanic lithosphere, partial melting, melt-rock interaction, and mantle melt fractionation⁽⁴⁾. In particular, abyssal peridotites are remnants of partially melted mantle below MOR, while highly depleted SSZ-type peridotites are mantle rocks that have undergone intense melting above subduction zones⁽²⁾.

The MOC consists of well-preserved mantle peridotite and chromite with a minor amount of mafic and felsic rocks along with Oceanic Pelagic Sediments (OPS). The mantle peridotite consists predominantly of harzburgite and lherzolite⁽⁵⁾. Serpentinized peridotite is the major component of the MOC while intrusive and extrusive mafic rocks form the minor components. The residual ultramafic rocks of lherzolite and harzburgite in the MOC are derivatives of spinel lherzolite that have undergone varying degrees of partial melting⁽⁶⁾. The MOC shows wide variation in its geochemical composition.

Several workers have studied the Naga-Manipur Ophiolite Belt (NMOB) in various aspects such as the NMOB consists of tectonic peridotite, mafic-ultramafic cumulate, mafic volcanic and dykes, plagiogranite, and OPS^(1,7). It was reported to have formed in the SSZ, possibly during forearc-back arc magmatism when the India plate was subducting beneath the Myanmar plate^(2,7,8). The ophiolite formed in the spreading center of MOR or Plume-type features^(9,10). The serpentinites are the predominant rock type in the MOC area and have been largely neglected. In this present investigation, the main emphasis is given to the petrology and geochemical aspects like petrography, major, trace, and Rare Earth Elements (REE) of the area to understand and also correlate the protolith and geotectonic setting of these serpentinite rocks and characterize the nature of NMOB exposures in larger extent.

1.1 Geological Setting

The NMOB within the Alpine-Himalayan orogenic system forms a prominent NNE-SSW trending arcuate belt along the Indo-Myanmar Range (IMR). This belt is a part of the Arakan Yoma-Chin Hills-Naga Hills flysch trough, which dates back to the Upper Cretaceous to the Middle Eocene. This ophiolite appears as irregular tectonic blocks along the eastern margin of the IMR and extends up to the Andaman-Nicobar Islands. The NMOB is interpreted as an accretionary prism formed by the convergence of the Indian plate with the Myanmar plate⁽¹¹⁾. The ophiolitic rocks within the Indo-Myanmar Orogenic Belt (IMOB) show extensive tectonic deformation and fragmentation, reflecting three distinct phases of geological events similar to both the Himalayan orogeny and seafloor spreading observed in the Indian Ocean. These dismembered basic and ultrabasic rocks are closely associated with oceanic pelagic sediments and occur as folded thrust slices that overlay distal shelf sedimentary rocks ranging from the Eocene to Oligocene periods⁽⁹⁾.

The MOC thrusts over the Disang turbidites on the west, while the east of the state is covered by a very limited exposure of metamorphic rocks. These pre-Mesozoic metamorphic rocks, consisting of low to medium-grade phyllitic schist, quartzite, marble, and granite-gneiss, are considered the oldest unit in this region^(6,9). The ultramafic serpentinites represent the largest litho-unit, making up more than 90% of the igneous ophiolitic exposures with oceanic pelagic sediment and various blocks of exotic rocks. These exotic blocks are mainly Oceanic pelagic Shale-hosted while some of them especially gritty sandstones are found on Ultramafic rocks. The exposures of mafic rocks, including extrusive pillow lavas and diabasic dyke rocks which are sandwiched within the pelagic shale were also observed in the complex⁽⁶⁾. The ophiolite complex is placed within the Disang Group of the Eocene to Upper Cretaceous age. The study area lies in the southeastern sector of the Tengnoupal district within Manipur state, as illustrated (Figure 1a and b). The ultramafic rock suite in this region predominantly comprises mantle peridotites, which are closely related to pelagic sediments such as chert, conglomerates, slates, and shales. The residual mantle peridotite mainly consists of metamorphosed harzburgite and lherzolite, while the remaining 10% is made up of basic dykes and sills and volcanic rocks, including pillow lavas⁽⁶⁾. The petrogenetic and structural characteristics of the NMOB reflect the evolution of the Tethyan oceanic crust and upper mantle. This development occurred in a changing geodynamic environment characterized by SSZ forearc extension, subduction initiation, and continental arc accretion⁽¹⁾. The ultramafic serpentinitized

peridotites of a Neo-Tethyan mantle wedge underwent varying degrees of mantle metasomatism and partial melting⁽⁸⁾. The belt is thought to have formed in a complex tectonic setting involving MOR and subduction zone processes⁽¹²⁾.

Fig 1. a) Generalized geological map of Manipur Northeast India and b) Geological map of the study area in MOC of Tengnoupal

2 Methodology

In this study, detailed fieldwork was carried out in which 30 representative rock samples were collected from the study area (Figure 1b). These samples were sent to the Department of Geological Sciences, Gauhati University, Guwahati for slide preparation. Out of these, 10 samples were selected for geochemical analyses for this work. Petrographic analyses were carried out using a Leica DME2700P petrological microscope equipped with a Leica DFC420 camera and Leica Image analysis software (LAS-V.4.6) at the Department of Geology, Mizoram University.

Whole-rock analysis for major, trace, and rare earth elements (REE) was carried out at the Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology in Dehradun, India. Major oxides and trace elements were determined using an X-ray Fluorescence spectrometer (XRF) on a Bruker S8 Tiger. The sample preparation involved drying powdered samples (200 mesh) at 105°C for 12 hours followed by high-temperature ashing at 1,000°C for 5 hours. The resulting materials were then cooled (400°C), and reweighed to determine the Loss on Ignition (LOI). The analytical precision was within ± 2% to 3% for major elements and ± 5% to 6% for trace elements. Rare earth elements were analyzed using a Quadrupole Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (TQ-ICP-MS; Perkin Elmer SCIEX ELAN DRC-II). The comprehensive geochemical data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Whole-rock of Major, trace, and rare earth elements of Serpentinite rocks in MOC

Sample	HZ25	HZ26	HZ27	HP8	HP9	HP12	HP13	HP14	HP16	HP18
Major oxide elements (wt.%)										
SiO ₂	41.29	41.06	42.02	41.03	39.94	41.28	40.11	40.73	40.32	41.60
Al ₂ O ₃	2.40	2.29	3.01	2.27	2.27	2.50	2.07	2.34	2.78	0.95
Fe ₂ O ₃	6.35	5.71	8.03	7.22	7.50	7.93	8.24	7.82	7.34	5.11
CaO	0.99	0.58	1.61	1.06	0.77	1.72	0.41	0.69	1.79	0.02
MgO	38.50	39.60	36.13	38.90	39.28	37.84	40.07	38.21	38.69	42.60
K ₂ O	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Na ₂ O	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04
MnO	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.13	0.11	0.09	0.11	0.08	0.07
TiO ₂	0.07	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.00
P ₂ O ₅	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	89.77	89.47	91.05	90.72	90.01	91.52	91.09	90.00	91.12	90.39
LOI	14.09	14.04	13.89	12.45	13.43	13.20	12.22	14.37	12.81	13.44
Mg#	87	88	83	86	85	72	84	84	85	90
MgO/SiO ₂	0.93	0.96	0.86	0.95	0.98	0.92	0.99	0.94	0.96	1.02
Al ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.02
Trace elements (ppm)										
Ba	-	-	9	-	-	-	-	16	9	13
Cr	3816	3516	3489	3188	2817	3189	2916	2987	2839	628
V	74	62	89	78	74	90	77	67	78	6
Sc	14	13	11	12	14	13	13	9	10	-
Co	126	124	31	114	99	108	114	71	54	114
Ni	2347	2710	4074	2269	2264	2369	2265	3331	3236	2921
Cu	36	14	26	23	20	22	21	19	6	32
Zn	53	55	47	64	47	58	48	49	30	38
Ga	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pb	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Th	-	2.1	-	1.3	1.8	2.1	-	0.1	1.4	1.5
Rb	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.7
Sr	-	-	-	1	6	1	2	1	-	-
Y	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	6	3
Zr	-	3	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nb	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Rare earth elements (ppm)										
La	0.022	0.022	0.062	0.074	0.010	0.030	0.002	0.346	1.778	0.032
Ce	0.108	0.078	0.036	0.200	0.056	0.074	0.020	0.112	0.248	0.098
Pr	0.014	0.012	0.010	0.018	0.006	0.008	0.000	0.016	0.270	0.004
Nd	0.086	0.070	0.046	0.092	0.056	0.056	0.008	0.060	0.536	0.028
Sm	0.104	0.068	0.046	0.064	0.060	0.084	0.014	0.050	0.222	0.006
Eu	0.040	0.024	0.022	0.028	0.032	0.034	0.006	0.022	0.068	0.010
Gd	0.182	0.120	0.100	0.128	0.138	0.168	0.034	0.108	0.352	0.006
Tb	0.040	0.026	0.022	0.026	0.030	0.038	0.008	0.022	0.058	0.000
Dy	0.310	0.202	0.166	0.220	0.244	0.310	0.074	0.192	0.420	0.006
Ho	0.076	0.048	0.040	0.052	0.060	0.076	0.018	0.048	0.104	0.002
Er	0.224	0.140	0.128	0.162	0.176	0.222	0.060	0.140	0.298	0.006

Continued on next page

Table 1 continued

Tm	0.038	0.022	0.020	0.026	0.030	0.038	0.010	0.022	0.046	0.002
Yb	0.236	0.166	0.124	0.198	0.204	0.256	0.064	0.172	0.284	0.010
Lu	0.038	0.026	0.020	0.030	0.032	0.042	0.010	0.028	0.048	0.002
ΣREE	1.518	1.024	0.842	1.318	1.134	1.436	0.328	1.338	4.732	0.212
ΣLREE	0.374	0.274	0.222	0.476	0.220	0.286	0.050	0.606	3.122	0.178
ΣHREE	1.144	0.750	0.620	0.842	0.914	1.150	0.278	0.732	1.610	0.034
(La/Yb)N	0.063	0.090	0.339	0.254	0.033	0.079	0.021	1.366	4.253	2.174
(Gd/Yb)N	0.624	0.585	0.652	0.523	0.547	0.530	0.429	0.508	1.003	4.485
(Ce/Sm)N	0.257	0.284	0.194	0.775	0.231	0.218	0.354	0.555	0.277	4.050
Eu/Eu*	0.857	0.783	0.956	0.912	1.037	0.844	0.810	0.882	0.717	4.912
Ce/Ce*	1.482	1.156	0.348	1.320	1.741	1.151	3.551	0.362	0.086	2.086

LOI: Loss on Ignition; Mg#: Magnesium number and -: Below detection limit.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Petrography:

The serpentinite rocks of the MOC found in Haolenphai and New Mongjang villages of the Tengnoupal area, are mainly composed of olivine and pyroxene and exhibit varying degrees of serpentization. According to the thin section, pseudomorphic textures such as mesh and hourglass textures after olivine and bastites after pyroxene minerals (orthopyroxene) as well as fibrous structures, filling the veins by chrysotile are observed (Figure 2a, b, c & d). The presence of abundant bastite suggests that the original rock, or protolith, was likely harzburgite. Olivines are anhedral to subhedral and range from 0.3 to 0.5 mm in diameter and highly fractured and these grains display hourglass texture indicating significant metamorphic processes. Orthopyroxene appears as pale brownish, subhedral grains, often forming large porphyroclasts up to a centimeter in size. Many orthopyroxene porphyroclasts have experienced significant deformation, undulatory extinction, and kink banding providing evidence of strain effect (Figure 2e). Also, in some bastite sections, rare exsolution lamellae of clinopyroxene (Cpx) are also preserved and talc or chlorite alteration primarily occurring along the cleavage planes (Figure 2f), and exhibit lobate grain boundaries. Opaque minerals like chromium-spinel and magnetite are also observed, and the cr-spinel grains are more abundant than the magnetite. They are characterized by their brown to reddish-brown color often found along olivine fractures and also occur between pyroxene and serpentinite indicating formation before serpentization (Figure 2g). It also has an opaque Fe-rich that resembles magnetite rims. In addition, secondary magnetite minerals have formed along grain boundaries and fractures due to the weathering of mafic minerals.

3.2 Major oxide elements:

Bulk rock major elements of ten chosen samples of the serpentinite rocks from the MOC are given in Table 1. The analyzed sample's Loss on Ignition (LOI) ranges from 12.22 to 14.37 wt.%. These relatively high LOI values indicate significant serpentization of olivine and pyroxene, as supported by petrographic analysis. The low SiO₂ content of the samples ranges from 39.94 to 41.60 wt.%. The majority of the samples contain high MgO ranging from 36.13 to 42.60 wt.%; low Al₂O₃ values ranging from 0.95 to 3.01 wt.% and the magnesium number (Mg#) between 72–90 wt.%. The major elements of the studied ultramafic rocks in MOC align with metamorphic peridotites on the ACM (Al₂O₃-CaO- MgO) and AFM [(Na₂O-K₂O)-FeO-MgO] of the ternary diagram (Figure 3 a and b)⁽¹³⁾. This suggests that the serpentinites examined represent a depleted or residual mantle. These results are further supported by high Mg# values. In particular, Mg# values of some of the samples examined are 84.40, which is close to the primitive mantle value of 89 (Sun and Mc Donough 1989) and comparable to the Mg# values found in residual peridotites. According to [(FeO_t+TiO₂)-Al₂O₃-MgO], the ternary diagram illustrates the komatiitic affinity of serpentinite rocks⁽¹⁴⁾ (Figure 3 c).

The rocks studied have a higher Mg/Si ratio (ranging from 0.85 to 1.02 with an average value of 0.89) compared to the primitive mantle value (0.85), but a lower Al/Si ratio (ranging from 0.023 to 0.072 with an average value of 0.040) than the primitive mantle PM value 0.1 (Sun and Mc Donough 1989). The Al/Si ratios in the serpentinite rocks were often lower than the PM value of 0.1 (Sun and Mc Donough 1989) but greater than the highly depleted mantle residual harzburgites, which had an Al/Si ratio of approximately 0.02. The lower Al₂O₃/SiO₂ ratios in the serpentinite peridotites relative to the PM values suggest that the protoliths partially melted before serpentization⁽¹⁵⁾. The variation diagram of major oxide elements (Figure 4), where Al₂O₃ was utilized as a depletion index among the least mobile elements to understand better specific elements' behavior⁽¹⁵⁾. Major oxide elements like MgO have a negative correlation and Na₂O does not correlate with

Fig 2. Photomicrograph of serpentinite rocks under cross-polarized light (XPL) showing a) a mesh texture indicative of serpentinization within the peridotite and fine-grained magnetite filled along the boundary; b) hourglass textures of serpentine pseudomorphs replacing olivine; c) bastite pseudomorphs originating from orthopyroxene (Opx); d) Fibrous chrysotile veins observed in serpentinized ultramafic; e) Kink banding and undulatory extinction in Orthopyroxene; f) Orthopyroxene exsolve clinopyroxene (cpx) lamellae in serpentinite rocks; g) Chrome-Spinel occurs in between pyroxene and serpentinite; h) Serpentine mineral with alteration of Olivine and pyroxene

Fig 3. Ternary plots of a) ACM (Al_2O_3 -CaO-MgO); b) AFM [$(\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O})$ -FeO-MgO]; c) $(\text{FeO}_t + \text{TiO}_2)$ - Al_2O_3 -MgO diagram, for the studied serpentinite rocks in MOC

Al_2O_3 , whereas SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , Na_2O , and TiO_2 are covariant with Al_2O_3 . The samples also had low CaO contents ranging from 0.02 to 1.72 wt.%, and given CaO's high mobility, its depletion shows that clinopyroxene change is accompanied by Ca dissolution^(16,17). Furthermore, the examined serpentinites peridotites fall into the fields of abyssal mantle peridotites when major oxide compositions are compared to Al_2O_3 indicating a strong affinity with this mantle peridotite (Figure 4).

3.3 Trace and Rare earth elements:

The serpentinite rock samples are rich in transition metals such as Cr (628 to 3816 ppm), Ni (2264 to 4074 ppm), Co (31 to 126 ppm), V (6 to 90 ppm), and Cu (6 to 36 ppm), indicating their mantle origin. A trace element versus Al_2O_3 variation diagram (Figure 5)⁽¹⁵⁾ shows that the majority of the samples correspond to mantle peridotites, including both abyssal and ophiolitic types. Elements such as Ni and Cr enrich the primitive mantle (PM) due to their compatibility with mantle minerals such as olivine and spinel. Furthermore, Yb versus Al_2O_3 trends show a positive correlation with Al_2O_3 in the tectonically emplaced abyssal peridotites.

The studied rocks show a significant depletion of rare earth elements (REE) and a low abundance of ΣREE . Chondrite-normalized REE (after McDonough and Sun 1995) patterns are slightly concave-up, displaying depletion in light REE (LREE), and are relatively flat in heavy REE (HREE), resembling a spoon (Figure 9a). The depletion in LREE (La/Yb)_N = 0.021–4.253 is relatively more as compared to HREE (Gd/Yb)_N = 0.429–1.002 and middle REE (MREE; Ce/Sm)_N = 0.218–4.050).

Fig 4. Plots of selected major versus Al_2O_3 of the studied Serpentinite rocks a) MgO vs. Al_2O_3 ; b) CaO vs. Al_2O_3 ; c) SiO_2 vs. Al_2O_3 ; d) Fe_2O_3 vs. Al_2O_3 ; e) Na_2O vs. Al_2O_3 and f) TiO_2 vs. Al_2O_3 . The light purple fields are of orogenic, ophiolitic, and abyssal mantle peridotites

Their REE patterns show positive Ce (Ce/Ce^* : 0.348–3.552 with an average value of 1.33) and Eu (Eu/Eu^* : 0.717–4.913 with an average of 1.27) anomalies. The observed positive Eu anomaly and the increase in LREE/HREE observed in the serpentinite can be attributed to the action of hydrothermal fluid. This is because serpentinites like their source rocks are depleted in REE. Serpentinite samples show negative anomalies for elements including Rb, Sr, Ce, and Eu, and positive anomalies for U, Y, and La on the multi-element diagrams normalized to the primitive mantle (after Sun and McDonough 1989). Their incompatible immobile elements ranging from Gd to Lu exhibit flat patterns, similar to those observed in abyssal peridotites⁽¹⁵⁾ (Figure 9 b).

Fig 5. Selected trace elements binary plots against Al_2O_3 ; a) Cr vs. Al_2O_3 ; b) Ni vs. Al_2O_3 ; c) Sm vs. Al_2O_3 and d) Yb vs Al_2O_3 . Orogenic, ophiolitic, and abyssal mantle peridotites (light purple fields)

Fig 6. a) Plots showing CaO vs. Al_2O_3 wt.% variation diagram of the studied serpentinite rocks. b) Whole-rock MgO/SiO_2 vs. Al_2O_3/SiO_2 ; c) Bulk-rock Al_2O_3 (wt. %) contents of serpentinites in MOC compared with those from other tectonic settings and the Pan-African serpentinites d) The Dy/Yb versus La/Yb plot for the serpentinite rocks indicates their formation at relatively shallow depths within the spinel-peridotite stability field

Fig 7. a) SiO₂-FeO*-MgO triangular diagram and (b) relationship between serpentinites and their protoliths in a MgO-Al₂O₃-CaO (wt%) ternary diagram of the studied serpentinite rocks

Fig 8. Binary plots of a) U (ppm); b) Sr (ppm); c) Ti (ppm) against Yb (ppm) for the analyzed serpentinite rocks (the compositions of the primitive mantle, global subducting sediments (GLOSS), and sediments are included for comparison) and d) The Ti/1000 vs. V plot separates MORB, island arc tholeiite (IAT), and boninite magma types

Fig 9. a) Chondrite-normalized pattern of REE and b) Primitive mantle-normalized pattern of trace and REE. Field of abyssal peridotite (Grey) and field of fore-arc peridotites (Light yellow)

4 Discussion

4.1 Nature and Origin of Serpentinites:

On the Al_2O_3 and CaO Binary diagram (Figure 6a)⁽¹⁶⁾, the studied serpentinite rocks correspond to abyssal peridotite. On the SiO_2/MgO versus $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ diagram (Figure 6b)⁽¹⁶⁾ the analyzed samples fall below the trend line for the 'mantle terrestrial array,' indicating a magmatic depletion (or enrichment) trend from primitive mantle compositions to highly depleted harzburgitic compositions. The majority of the samples fall within the abyssal peridotite fields. Residues exhibit higher Mg/Si and lower Al/Si ratios, whereas melts show the opposite with lower Mg/Si and higher Al/Si ratios. According to Niu (2004), abyssal serpentinites are characterized by low $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ ratios (below 0.035) and MgO/SiO_2 ratios ranging from 0.8 and 1.2. In contrast, abyssal peridotites have $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ ratios ranging from 0.01 to 0.07 and MgO/SiO_2 ratios from 0.75 to 1.05. According to Le Maitre (1976), work suggests that average MgO/SiO_2 and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ ratios for specific rock types are 0.83 and 0.05 for harzburgite, 0.66 and 0.09 for lherzolite, and 0.99 and 0.04 for dunite, respectively.⁽¹⁷⁾ Meanwhile, the serpentinite rocks in MOC have MgO/SiO_2 values between 0.86 and 1.02 with an average value of 0.95. The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ values ratio ranges between 0.05 and 0.07 with an average value of 0.04, likely resembling dunite. Also, on the plot of the Fe_2O_3 - SiO_2 -MgO and the CaO- Al_2O_3 -MgO tri-plot, the studied samples plot in harzburgite with minor dunite (Figure 7a and b).⁽¹⁸⁾ Therefore the studied serpentinites of MOC corresponds to a protolith of harzburgite and minor dunite. The serpentinite peridotites show a refractory nature, evidenced by high MgO/SiO_2 and high Al_2O_3 content (average = 2.29) which is relatively unaffected by serpentinization and therefore retains its original primary signature (Figure 6 c), similar to abyssal peridotites found at mid-ocean ridge settings⁽¹⁹⁾. Al/Si ratio ranges from 0.023 to 0.072 which indicates that these serpentinites are the refractory depleted mantle protolith and are lower than the primitive mantle (PM ~ 0.1) values but higher than highly depleted mantle residual harzburgites (~ 0.02). So, the depletion of Al in the analyzed samples represents refractory peridotite residues that have undergone partial melting, as Al is slightly incompatible with mantle minerals and is depleted during the processes. Thus, the studied serpentinites are derived from the alteration of harzburgite with a limited dunite protolith composition. This finding is in contrast with the existing view that the MOC is primarily derived from lherzolitic protoliths.

The studied serpentinites rocks in the Dy/Yb versus La/Yb variation diagram correspond to Spinel-peridotite facies (Figure 6d). Dick and Bullen (1984) proposed a component of plagioclase peridotites, which make up ~30 vol% of abyssal peridotites on the seafloor, but plagioclase is absent in all the studied samples. The very low Ca (0.02–1.79 wt%) and Na (0.04–0.06 wt.%) contents in these samples give the clue that the original amount of plagioclase was low and was altered during serpentinization⁽¹⁶⁾. The results also showed depletion of major and trace elements in the rock compared to PM values. The depletion of rare earth elements (REE) and high-field-strength elements (HFSE) relative to PM has been observed in orogenic, abyssal, and ophiolite peridotites^(15,16), indicating their origin as mantle melting residues.

4.2 Geo-tectonic environments:

Serpentinization occurs in various tectonic settings and is caused by the hydration of mafic or ultramafic rocks through interaction with fluids from different sources. Serpentinization of mantle rocks typically occurs during ocean-floor metamorphism at mid-ocean ridges and through dynamic metamorphism at subduction zones⁽²⁰⁾. Previous workers^(21,22) have demonstrated that the geochemistry of serpentinites is closely linked to their tectonic settings. Ocean-floor metamorphism results in the mobilization of trace elements like Rb and Sr, enrichment of Pb and Sb through carbonate precipitation, and U-enrichment due to hydrothermal alteration⁽¹⁶⁾. The titanium (Ti) contents of bulk rock are often used to determine the tectonic settings in which serpentinite is formed since Ti tends to remain stable and unchanged during serpentinization and is not significantly affected during melt-rock interactions. Specifically, mantle wedge serpentinites are characteristic of low bulk rock Ti content (2–50 ppm), while abyssal and subducted serpentinites have higher Ti concentrations, ranging from 10 to 130 ppm and above 50 ppm, respectively⁽²³⁾.

The studied serpentinite rocks show depletion in Rb and Sr and exhibit high LOI (average = 13.39 wt.%), indicating seafloor alteration. To assess the influence of subduction on SSZ lavas, various researchers plot mafic-ultramafic rocks on a Ti/1000 vs. variation diagram. Titanium (Ti) is highly incompatible and decreases with increasing partial melting, while vanadium (V) remains immobile and exhibits incompatible behavior under oxidizing conditions with the presence of fluids. The melting regime triggered by subduction fluids leads to depletion in Ti and enrichment in V. As a result, the ratio of Ti/V greater than 20 is typical of MORB, intermediate ratios (10-20) occur in island arc tholeiites, and lower ratios (<10) are commonly found in boninites. Thus, the serpentinized rocks have low Ti/V ratios ranging from 3.89 to 5.80, fitting within the boninite data range, suggesting formation at higher oxidizing conditions during subduction initiation (Figure 8d). The high Ti concentrations (averages = 400) are comparable to those of subducted serpentinites strongly support a subduction-related setting (Figure 8 a, b

&c)⁽²⁴⁾. The high Cr contents and spinel protolith compositions indicate that the parent magmas were generated in a subduction environment, particularly in a Supra-Subduction Zone setting⁽²⁵⁾.

5 Conclusions

Comprehensive petrographic and geochemical analyses of serpentinite rocks in the MOC area have significantly expanded our understanding of their genesis and evolution. The sample shows mesh and hourglass textures pseudomorph after olivine and bastites after pyroxene. Higher Mg numbers (Mg# average 84.4), with high Cr (628 - 3816 ppm) and Ni (2264 to 4074 ppm) contents a komatiitic affinity of the studied samples originated from cumulate-derived mantle peridotite. The high LOI, low Al₂O₃/SiO₂ (0.02 to 0.07 wt.%), and high MgO/SiO₂ (0.86-1.02 wt.%) compared to the primitive mantle also suggest mantle residual harzburgite with limited dunite that had undergone varying degrees of serpentinization, which is similar to the oceanic abyssal peridotites. This study also reveals a unique transitional phase between abyssal and subduction-related serpentinite indicating a complex process occurring in supra-subduction environments. The high-Ti (> 50 ppm) content in the bulk rocks with boninitic mantle melt and spoon-shaped REE signatures indicates the subduction initiation. Therefore, the studied serpentinite rocks in MOC are derived in two distinct tectonic environments of abyssal or mid-oceanic ridge and subduction. More studies on the serpentinite rocks in MOC could offer important information about the evolution of supra-subduction environments together with the related magmatic & metamorphic processes. The results are also crucial for grasping the evolution of Earth's mantle and oceanic crust development through time, as well as the formation of economic mineral deposits related to ultramafic rocks. Further studies should focus on detailed mineralogy and P-T conditions of the ultramafic rocks and may give us a better understanding of the protolith's composition and evolution of these rocks.

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